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The Impact of Force Majeure on the Development and Organisation of Film Festival Activities in Ukraine

Abstract: *Introduction.* Organising film festivals is an important process for the country's film industry development. This process requires specific skills on the part of the organisers, as well as careful attention to the organisation as a whole. A study of the development of film festivals in the country is necessary as it helps to identify young talent. Film festivals have always played a crucial role in the film industry development in different countries. For the further development of the Ukrainian film industry, it is important to study the experience of organising festivals and understand the impact of unforeseen circumstances on them. *Purpose and methods.* The purpose of the article is to substantiate the theoretical foundations and develop practical recommendations for organising film festivals. The work was based on the abstract and logical method, the method of analysis and synthesis, and the critical analysis of scientific literature, which allowed us to summarise the theoretical and practical developments accumulated by the community in the context of film festival activities. *Results.* The essence, role, and significance of film festivals for the country's film industry development are revealed. The problems of organising film festivals in Ukraine are identified. Methods for improving the system of film festival organisation are formulated. The peculiarities of organising film festivals in Ukraine after 2020 are identified. *Conclusions.* The scientific novelty of the results obtained is to deepen the theoretical foundations of film festival organisation by summarising the best international experience in this segment of culture. The significance of the study is manifested in the expansion of knowledge in the field of film festival organisation and the impact of irresistible forces on it.

Keywords: film festival, festival, organisation, development, force majeure, socio-cultural sphere.

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1. Introduction

The problem formulation. The importance of studying the specifics of film festival organisation is not only theoretical but also practical, as projects of this type have a major impact on the development of the film industry as a whole.

The film industry, like other industries, is quite dependent on the business component. Thus, at the beginning of its existence, cinema was entertainment that brought income, and only then art. Both in 1895 and in 2023, films cannot be made on their own, and cinema always requires a large amount of resources, both human and financial (Fandorina, 2019). In the film industry, the main goal is to distribute the final product (film), and it is crucial for authors to have their work bought not only by local but also foreign film distributors, which will help promote the work and its author.

Thus, the main reason for the rapid development of the film festival industry is an attempt to provide new filmmakers with the opportunity to present their projects to a wide audience and receive feedback. Today, film festivals continue to fulfil their function as a political, artistic, and business arena (Lee, 2012).

Recently, there has been a special need to study and research the organisation of film festivals, as irreversible changes have taken place in the world. The film industry, like any other industry, is heavily influenced by political, social, and other global changes. Therefore, there is a need to study the impact of force majeure on the organisation of film festivals not only in the world but also in Ukraine.

State study of the problem. The general theoretical foundations of socio-cultural activities management are set out in the works of Ya. Martynyshyn, O. Khlystun, and Ye. Kovalenko (Martynyshyn & Khlystun, 2018, 2019; Martynyshyn & Kovalenko, 2016, 2017, 2018; Martynyshyn et al., 2020, 2022, 2023; Kovalenko, 2017, 2018, 2019, 2020, 2022, 2023) and other scholars.

A great contribution to the development of a wide range of issues related to the organisation of film festivals has been made by such domestic and foreign scholars and practitioners as: S. Trymbach (2013), Yu. Okhrimenko (2015), E. Fandorina (2019), V. Myslavskyi (2007), C. H.-Y. Wong (2011), F. Lee (2012), R. Stephenson, A. Morphy, D. Andrew and R. Skliar (n.d.), T. Hryhorchuk (2007), S. Shevchenko (2021), K. Grabas (n.d.), M. Porter (2020), P. Eldridge and J. Voss (2001). These works examine various aspects of film festivals in different countries of the world.

Unresolved issues. Researchers have done a lot of work to highlight the principles, features, and specifics of film festival organisation.

Despite a sufficient number of works on the history of cinema as an art, film industry, film festival management, management of socio-cultural activities, etc., this topic still remains insufficiently studied, as every day, every year, changes in the industry and the world occur that require updating theoretical and practical knowledge.

The film industry is highly dependent on scientific and technological progress. Humanity does not stand still, and every year becomes more and more advanced in technology. To understand the prospects for development and the changes that have already taken place, you need to deepen your knowledge in the field of modern management of socio-cultural activities and film industry management and follow the trends in the development of the technological sphere.

Given the huge influence of the film industry on the socio-cultural sphere, it is necessary to trace the trends in the development of cinema activities in Ukraine, as it has an impact on the development of not only the cultural but also the economic spheres.

Cinema has a great influence on people's consciousness and worldview. By watching films, we have the opportunity to expand our knowledge in various fields, get to know different cultures, receive new information, and consolidate the old.

A film festival is a political, artistic and business arena. From the very beginning of its existence, film art has been influenced by various segments of the population. Thus, in some countries of the world, cinema was subjected to severe censorship and careful supervision of the film production process. The Motion Picture Code, also called the Hays Code, is a series of moral codes that regulated the production of American cinema from 1930–1968. Americans did not like the strict censorship of films and fought against the system, which gave us New Hollywood.

Another significant example is the use of propaganda in films, which is a very relevant and big problem for Ukraine today. Propaganda has always been used in cinema, just remember the famous director A. Hitlera, Leni Rifenshtal, who made propaganda films for Nazi Germany. One of the most famous is “Triumph des Willens” (1934), a film that had a very strong influence on people's minds as if zombifying them. That was back then, but if you watch this film today, people who have a weak psyche can be influenced by it.

Summing up all of the above, we understand that the film industry and film festivals attract the attention of a large number of people to film projects, and therefore this type of activity is a very effective means of promoting films to the audience. Therefore, it is worthwhile to understand all the intricacies of the process of organising film festivals to direct it in the right direction and make it work for yourself, for the development of culture and society.

2. Purpose and methods

The purpose and research tasks. The purpose of the article is to develop theoretical foundations and practical recommendations for improving film festivals organisation in Ukraine.

To achieve this purpose, the following tasks have been set:

- to reveal the essence and significance of film festival activities for artists and society;
- to identify the peculiarities of film festival organisation;
- to study the state and current trends in the development of the film festival market;
- to analyse the impact of force majeure on the organisation and development of film festivals in Ukraine.

Methodology and methods. The methodological basis of the study is the fundamental provisions of the theory of film festival organisation and management, scientific articles by domestic and foreign scholars on the problems of managing the organisation and development of film festivals. Systematic, historical, interdisciplinary, and methodological approaches allow us to consider festival activities as a holistic, open, dynamic system.

Both general scientific and special research methods were used in the article. To study the theoretical foundations of film festival organisation, the author used an abstract and logical approach to understanding the essence of organising and conducting film festivals, methods of analysis and synthesis, critical analysis of scientific literature, systematisation, and generalisation of scientific provisions. In the process of evaluating the effectiveness of the film festival management system, the following methods were used: system-structural, system-functional, balance sheet, strategic planning, and modelling.

Information base. The information base of the study includes scientific works of domestic and foreign scholars in the field of cinema history, film industry research, film industry and film festival management, as well as management of socio-cultural activities; the Law of Ukraine “On Cinematography” (Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine, 1998). The results of the study are also based on the author's own experience gained while working at “Kinolife” LLC, a film distribution and film festival organisation company.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. The essence and importance of film festivals for artists and society

Film festivals are an integral part of the film industry, ensuring its economic, social, and cultural development, the emergence of new talent, and coverage of events taking place in the film industry around the world (*Table 1*).

A film festival is a review, a creative competition of fiction, chronicle and documentary, popular science, educational, sports, animation, and television films (Myslavskyi, 2007, p. 261).

Table 1. The role of film festival activity in the development of film industry

Role	Manifestation forms
A platform for filmmakers	A platform for independent and emerging filmmakers to showcase their work to a wider audience and industry professionals
Feedback and training	Opportunity to get feedback on your work. Help to improve your skills and storytelling. Opportunity to learn from each other
Networking	Communication and information exchange with film professionals, such as producers, distributors and financiers, who can provide them with support and resources to further their careers
Diversity and cultural exchange	Cultural and leisure activities. A capacitor of creative experience. A cultural project and a cultural good. Expanding the perspectives of viewers and promoting understanding and compassion by screening films from different countries and cultures. Helping to improve the work of underrepresented groups
Competitive	A film festival is an arena for a creative competition.
Image	Improvement and consolidation of the artist's image in the minds of film festival visitors and film professionals
Economic	Promotes the career of little-known directors, producers, etc. A business link in the cultural and entertainment industry. A source of funding to complete or start a film project. Factors that increase demand for film services. Creating a market for independent films
Distribution	A catalyst for creating new film markets and distribution channels. An opportunity for a premiere for a film product. A film market. An alternative to film distribution
Insurance	Film festival is a factor that reduces possible risks in the film business

Source: own development

In Ukraine, the film festival market is not at a very high level, but despite this, some companies have a great influence on the industry. One of these companies is “Kinolife”, a film distribution and film festival organisation company. Over the years, the company has organised and held a large number of film festivals, including: “Best Horror Shorts”, “Best Comedy Shorts”, “Best Erotic Shorts”, “ZiFF” and many others. The company became the founder of the first international festival of innovative films “Kinnovation”. The company is also engaged in the films localisation it shows to a large audience.

Each of the festivals is accompanied by an event where the audience can meet directors, actors, project managers, and specialists from various fields. After the screening, the audience can vote for the best film.

Another area of the company's activity is the international organisation of film festivals, which include educational events for young people from European countries. The company, in cooperation with organisations such as “Erasmus+”, “Institute Kosmopolis”, “Kinograph” and others, organises useful educational film festivals in which young people can participate free of charge and receive a certificate of completion. Workshop speakers are well-known directors, screenwriters, producers, and other film professionals.

Film festivals are conditionally divided into two groups: “A” and “B”. Film festivals of type “A” must meet the following criteria, namely:

- have the most prestigious status compared to other festivals;
- have a competitive programme;
- be accredited by the International Federation of Association of Producers (FIAPF);
- there can be only one type of “A” festival in the country in which it is held.

Only 50 film festivals are accredited by the International Federation of Association of Producers. In Ukraine, there is only one film festival that is accredited by FIAPH – the Molodist Film Festival, which is held every year in Kyiv.

Until March 2022, the association had 52 festivals, but after the start of Russia's full-scale invasion of Ukraine, the federation decided to review the status of two film festivals held in Russia and revoke their accreditation.

Thus, based on the above, we see that the large-scale invasion of the aggressor country into the territory of the state of Ukraine had significant consequences for the development of the film industry and film festival activities in Russia.

It is also necessary to mention the “B” class festivals that did not receive accreditation due to non-compliance with the criteria and smaller organisational scale: in Ukraine (Kinnovation, Food Film Fest, Linoleum and others), Toronto (Toronto International Film Festival (TIFF)), Locarno (Locarno Film Festival) and other cities.

As mentioned above, the main purpose of film festivals is to distribute and sell the final product, namely films. Film festivals can provide the most effective and fastest way to achieve the filmmaker's goals of promoting their film product and popularising themselves as an author.

In recent years, due to the emergence and development of new technologies and the fact that information has become more accessible, many new talented artists have emerged who aim to make themselves known to the world. This is the reason why film festivals are so closely watched and why filmmakers are eager to participate in them, as they have become a necessary compensation for the monopolisation of film distribution and its concentration on a few of the most commercial film projects.

As Cindy Hing-Yuk Wong (2011) notes in her book “Film Festivals: Culture, People, and Power on the Global Screen”, early scholarship looked

at film festivals only as exhibition venues. In addition to this statement, Wong looks at film festivals as a place of knowledge production.

To sum up, we understand that film festivals attract the attention of a large part of society to the film industry, and therefore, this activity is a very effective means of promoting films to the audience.

Cultural and leisure activities contribute to the development of culture among different segments of the population through the art of cinema and thus contribute to the development of humanity as a whole. Film festivals also provide an opportunity for directors, producers and other artists from around the world to communicate with each other, share experiences, and negotiate cooperation, thus ensuring the exchange of information. Often, it is precisely this kind of communication that opens up new talents and new trends in the field of cinema to the world.

Film festivals provide an international marketplace where producers and distributors can exchange new ideas, screen films, and sign contracts. For the latter, film festivals are not only a way of communication but also a “market-place” where they can buy or sell films for further screening in cinemas around the world. Film festivals are also called a discussion platform for film art because they are usually attended by a large number of journalists, bloggers, photo reporters, and film critics representing reputable publications who cover the event and provide reviews.

So, taking all of the above into account, we conclude that film festivals play a significant role in the development of the film industry. They provide a platform for filmmakers and films that do not have the support of distributors and marketing companies and, therefore, are not able to easily gain the attention of a wide audience.

In this age of rapidly evolving technology and social media, film festivals offer a chance to stop and enjoy a moment, a film. They can teach people patience and the ability to experience things as they used to be, allowing them to be more than just a film viewer, involving them in the events creation, and offering the opportunity to connect through the sharing of unique experiences.

3.2. Features of organising film festivals

Despite the innovations in the field of film festival organisation that appear every year, the main stages of the organisation are preserved and followed. As with any other socio-cultural project, organising a film festival requires, first of all, defining the idea and goals of the future project. Film festivals can be organised by independent studios, government organisations, large studios, etc. Depending on the goals of a particular person or organisation, the preparation process may vary, but the “framework” remains the same.

After defining the idea, theme, and the film festival goals, you need to determine the target audience. To do this, you should analyse the competitors' market and create a portrait of the target audience.

A target audience is a group of people with similar interests and needs that a company can meet by selling its products.

The correct definition of the target audience can reduce costs and greatly facilitate the process of preparing and organising a film festival. One of the most common audience segmentation methods is the 5W methodology by Added Value, founder M. Sherrington (2003). This method is based on the law of marketing, which states that there is a product for every customer. The most effective and widespread method of competitor analysis is the method proposed by M. Porter (*Figure 1*).

Figure 1. Methodology of competitor analysis

Source: developed on the basis of (cited in: Hryhorchuk, 2007; Grabas, n.d.)

After completing the analysis of competitors, we will already have a clear understanding of what the future festival will be like, how to move correctly, and in which direction to organise it. Once all the stages have been successfully completed, you need to start creating and searching for funding resources for the upcoming event. This stage may include searching for partners, sponsors, investors, and other interested parties to raise money. Since a

partnership is a bilateral relationship, before entering into business relations with partners, you need to determine the benefits for all parties that cooperation can bring.

After successfully finding potential partners and concluding contracts, you need to think about setting up a planning committee and developing a clear division of responsibilities between your subordinates. After that, we determine a preliminary budget that cannot be exceeded and create and approve a business plan.

One of the key aspects of promoting and popularising a film festival is promotion. For a festival to be successful, it needs to be properly promoted to attract the attention of a wider audience.

Promotion is a systematic effort to create a successful, positive image through positive information transmission and thoughtful and planned long-term activities aimed at maintaining dialogue and mutually beneficial relations between an organisation and the groups on which its success depends.

Film festival promotion begins with the preparation of press releases and information materials. These materials help to share information about the film festival with business partners and the press. Another stage of promotion is social media promotions, which aims to advertise and promote the film festival to a wide range of viewers who can follow the preparations via social media, as well as those who will be the target of targeted advertising.

After successfully completing all the stages, you need to review the preliminary budget and create the final one. Then you can move on to finding sponsors and developing a comprehensive sponsorship proposal that clearly outlines the benefits of sponsoring the event. It's important to highlight the benefits of sponsoring the festival and explain how the sponsor's brand will benefit from the showcase. It is important to build strong relationships with sponsors for future events.

Even at the beginning of the film festival planning process, you need to start planning for project evaluation. This process should be an integral part of the festival planning, involving all team members.

3.3. The state and current trends of the film festival market

The film festival market is an important part of the global film industry, which is undergoing constant change and transformation. To successfully develop the film industry and get results, you need to understand the trends and changes taking place in this area. To do this, you need to pay attention to the fact that the number of festivals has grown dramatically in recent decades. This includes international, national, regional, and local film festivals. Each country and each of its regions can have its own film festival aimed at

promoting and developing the art of cinema, as well as at popularising the region in which the festival is held.

Nevertheless, international festivals such as the Cannes Film Festival, the Venice Film Festival, and the Berlin Film Festival remain key events in the world of cinema. They attract the world's most famous directors and actors and set new trends in the world of cinema. Nowadays, festivals are increasingly expanding their thematic scope to include films of different genres and styles. In addition to feature films, festivals also focus on documentaries, animation, short films, experimental cinema, and other art forms. This allows for the development of the filmmaker's vision and personal style.

The emergence of the internet and the events of 2020 (COVID-19) gave rise to a separate type of festival, online festivals. In recent years, many festivals have been actively developing their online presence. This allows viewers from all over the world to join the events, watch films, and take part in discussions, even if they cannot come to the festival in person. Festivals are increasingly collaborating with each other and with other cultural events. This can include film exchanges, joint projects, and partnerships with other artistic fields to facilitate cultural exchange.

In addition to the major festivals, there are smaller, specialised events dedicated to specific genres (e.g. horror, science fiction, LGBT film, etc.) or geographically limited (e.g. festivals dedicated to films from a particular country or region). Some film festivals are becoming increasingly commercially oriented, bringing films to market and using the festival as a platform to attract investment and promotional opportunities.

As already mentioned, film festivals are also affected by various challenges, such as the COVID-19 pandemic, financial difficulties, and competition with other forms of entertainment, and are responding to them by looking for new ways to develop and survive. Overall, the film festival market continues to expand, adapt, and change under the influence of new technologies, social and cultural changes, and remains an important platform for discovering new talent and promoting film art around the world.

The modern film festival market is undergoing numerous transformations and influences on global cinema and culture. Festivals are becoming more international, opening their doors to films from all over the world. This facilitates cultural exchange and helps to promote diverse cinematic traditions and voices.

In addition to traditional film screenings, festivals are adding other formats such as video games, virtual reality (VR), animation, short films, web series and documentaries. This opens up new opportunities for creativity and experimentation. Taking into account the Ukrainian film festival organising company "Kinolife", they launched a new format of film festivals in Ukraine, which took

place in autumn 2021 and was called “Kinnovation” – the first film festival of innovative cinema in Eastern Europe. The festival was a great success and popularity, so it was decided to organise this festival every year. However, due to the full-scale invasion in 2022, the company was forced to temporarily abandon this idea. Festivals actively include educational and cultural initiatives such as workshops, lectures, panel discussions and forums. This helps to increase film and media literacy and audiences, and make festivals more important educational events. “Kinolife”, together with its foreign partners, holds numerous master classes, workshops, and other educational events for young people interested in the film industry. In October 2023, in Olsztyn (Poland), “Kinolife”: and its partners are organising the “WAMA – FIELD – Film Industry European Leaders' Days” film festival. This project aims to share best practices from different countries, discuss opportunities for cooperation, improve brand-building and art promotion skills, increase knowledge of foreign film markets, and develop a network between European film industries. Young people will be able to develop a film project with a group and prepare a presentation for the final pitch.

Film festivals are actively using new technologies to expand their reach, including streaming platforms for online viewing and the use of artificial intelligence for film selection and recommendations.

Festival organisers are increasingly trying to focus on diversity, which means actively supporting women directors, social minorities, and other underrepresented groups in the film industry. Currently, to apply for an Oscar, you need to meet the requirements listed on the main Oscar website. Having a diverse team, providing favourable working conditions for disabled employees, and highlighting social issues in films (gender inequality, LGBT, etc.), to name but a few. Festivals often become platforms for social issues and activism. Films that address current issues receive a lot of attention and support.

Festivals are looking for new sources of funding and developing partnerships with sponsors, media companies and businesses. This helps to sustain festivals in an increasingly competitive environment. Some festivals try to maintain their independence from political influence and censorship to provide a free and open platform for the exchange of ideas and creativity. Some festivals are becoming not only platforms for screening films, but also important players in the process of finding talent and developing projects. For example, directors and producers can receive financial support or contracts with studios based on the success of their films at the festival.

Contemporary film festivals continue to play an important role in discovering new talent, creating a dialogue in society, and promoting the art of cinema. They are evolving, adapting to the changes in the modern world and remain an integral part of the world's cultural scene.

3.4. The impact of force majeure on the organisation and development of film festival activities in Ukraine

Force majeure, such as natural disasters, political conflicts and economic crises, can significantly affect the organisation and development of film festival activities in Ukraine, as in any other country.

As for the impact of the full-scale invasion of Ukraine by Russia, “Kinolife” suffered very serious losses and had to suspend its film festival activities in Ukraine, as cinemas were closed and large-scale events were banned.

Only now the company is starting to resume its activities in organising film festivals in Ukraine. In the summer of 2023, the first festival since the beginning of the war, “Best Erotic Shorts”, took place and was a huge success, which gave impetus to further organising film festivals and film distribution activities.

Taking into account the above, we can identify the following consequences of force majeure, namely:

- *Cancellation or postponement of film festivals:*

Natural disasters, such as floods, earthquakes, etc., can lead to the cancellation or postponement of planned film festivals. Also, political conflicts or epidemics, such as COVID-19, can force festival organisers to change their plans or suspend their activities, as we have already mentioned about “Kinolife”, which was forced to suspend its activities due to a full-scale invasion. Speaking of the COVID-19 pandemic, it also had an impact on the company. As people were unable to attend cinemas due to the closure of cinemas and the introduction of quarantine, the company was also forced to temporarily suspend its film festival activities.

- *Economic difficulties, financial losses and restrictions:*

Economic crises can significantly affect the funding of film festivals. Sponsors may lose interest in festivals and government financial support may decrease. This may lead to restrictions on the events, the choice of venues and the size of prize funds.

- *Changing the format and opening up new opportunities:*

In response to force majeure, festivals may change their format. For example, during the COVID-19 pandemic, many festivals switched to an online format to remain active. This may open up new opportunities for the further development of film festival activities and the film industry in general.

- *Socio-cultural changes:*

Political and geopolitical events can affect the socio-cultural context of a country, which can be reflected in the themes and structure of the films screened at festivals. Festivals can become platforms for expressing civic positions and reflecting important social issues.

- *International cooperation and relations:*

The conditions created by force majeure may force festival organisers to work more closely with international partners to ensure stability and support.

- *Political conflicts and geopolitical situation:*

Ukraine is going through a difficult period of political conflicts and geopolitical instability, in particular after the Euromaidan events and the annexation of Crimea by Russia. And also after the full-scale invasion of Ukraine by the aggressor country on 24 February 2022. This has affected the organisation of film festivals due to reduced security and uncertainty in the country. These events may also lead to changes in political leadership and financial support for cultural events, and therefore have a major impact on film festivals.

- *Security of film festivals:*

Force majeure, such as political conflicts or economic crises, can affect the security of film festivals. Increasing instability may require additional security measures to protect guests and participants.

- *Public support and audience:*

An important factor for festivals is the support of the audience. Irresistible forces can affect the general state of public opinion and interest in cultural events. In such circumstances, it can be difficult for film festival organisers in Ukraine to ensure the sustainability and development of their events. To overcome these challenges, it is important to have flexible strategies, contingency plans and adaptation strategies. It is also important to establish international partnerships and attract international support to ensure the sustainability and development of the film festival scene in Ukraine.

We can see the influence of almost all factors in Ukraine now, as the film industry, namely the organisation of film festivals, was very seriously affected by the economic crisis, the events of 2014, the COVID-2019 pandemic, and the war that began in 2022. The country has lost its stability, so we feel and will feel all the changes that these events will bring. We need to be prepared for this and start planning adaptation and stabilisation measures now.

4. Conclusions

The results of the study allowed us to define the concept of film festivals and the peculiarities of its organisation and development. Also, to consider and investigate the impact of irresistible forces on the development and organisation of film festivals in Ukraine and to draw the following conclusions:

1. Film festivals are an important tool for the development of the film industry and the cultural space in general. They contribute to economic, social and cultural development, as well as discover new talents and provide access to the latest events in the world of cinema. “Kinolife” in Ukraine plays an

important role in this area by organising various film festivals and promoting the development of cinema. Film festivals facilitate the exchange of information between artists from different countries, promote the development of the international film market and create a discussion platform for film art. In general, film festivals play an important role in the promotion and development of film art, as well as contribute to cultural exchange and the development of society.

2. The importance of proper preparation for the organisation of film festivals, the main stages and rules of promotion are established. Defining the idea, goals, and target audience are the first steps in organising a film festival. Competitor and market analysis also plays an important role in planning. Finding funding and partners, as well as setting up a planning committee, are necessary steps for the successful implementation of the project. Promotion, including press releases and social media promotion, is a very important aspect to attract the attention of potential audiences. Planning the evaluation of the project is also an important step to ensure the successful implementation of the film festival and the possibility of its further holding.

3. The film festival market is an important component of the global film industry, and it is currently undergoing significant change and development. Recent trends include an increase in the number of festivals, a diversity of themes and formats, the active development of online film festivals, cooperation between international festivals and the influence of the commercial component. In addition, the market is facing challenges, such as the pandemic and financial difficulties, and is forced to adapt to them. Overall, film festivals remain an important platform for the development of cinema and cultural exchange around the world. The modern film festival market is also undergoing numerous transformations that are affecting global cinema and culture. Increasing globalisation and diversity of formats, active educational activities and the use of innovative technologies, openness to different voices and social issues, as well as the search for new sources of funding and the struggle for independence from political influence are just some of the important aspects that characterise the development of film festivals. They remain important cultural and educational events, contributing to the development of cinema and creating a platform for the exchange of ideas in the modern world.

4. Force majeure, such as natural disasters, political conflicts and economic crises, have a significant impact on the organisation and development of film festival activities in Ukraine. Film festival organisers in Ukraine who have been affected by force majeure are forced to adapt to the conditions, postpone or cancel events, change formats and attract international support to ensure stability. Despite these challenges, it is important to develop flexible strategies and continue to maintain the interest of viewers and audiences to ensure the further development of film festivals in Ukraine.

The scientific novelty. The scientific novelty of the results obtained is to deepen the theoretical foundations of film festival organisation based on the generalisation of the best international experience in this field of culture.

The significance of the study. The significance of the study lies in the expansion of knowledge in the field of organisation and development of film festivals and the possibility of using it in the process of organising and studying film festival activities.

Prospects for further research. The prospect of further research in this area may be the development of a unique scheme for the organisation and development of film festivals and the film industry in general in Ukraine.

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